

Elementary Idea of Using LHC as an Information Storage

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July 2, 2024

Abstract

This short idea suggests that LHC can be used as an information storage based on the holographic property of mini black hole produced while controllable amount of collisions happen.

1 Introduction

Current understanding of mini black hole inside LHC is focused on its evaporation [[Hawking\(1974\)](#), [Giddings and Thomas\(2002\)](#)]. But another possible situation can be questioned – if stable amount of black holes can be produced while their topological behaviors conserved in multitude of collisions, LHC can be used as an information storage.

2 Example Case: Storing Cat Photo

For realization, simple use case of storing cat photo in black hole can be suggested¹. Suppose that topological properties of black hole can be repeatably reproduced while multitudes of collisions in LHC, mini black hole with Hawking radiation happens with its own scale of energy.

For default property of mini black hole with size of $1\text{\AA}$:

$$(\text{radius of mini black hole})r_s = \frac{1\text{\AA}}{2} = \frac{10^{-10}m}{2} = 5 \times 10^{-11}m$$

With calculating its event horizon area A :

$$A = 4\pi r_s^2 \Rightarrow A = 4\pi(5 \times 10^{-11})^2 \\ \Rightarrow A \approx 3.14 \times 10^{-20}m^2$$

Then the information entropy of blackhole turns out to be as:

$$S = \frac{kA}{4l_p^2} \\ \text{s.t. Boltzmann constant } K \approx 1.38 \times 10^{-23}J/K, \\ \text{Planck length } l_p \approx 1.616 \times 10^{-35}m \\ \Rightarrow S \approx 4.15 \times 10^{26}J/K$$

With turning entropy into bytes:

$$4.15 \times 10^{26}bits \approx 5.19 \times 10^{25}bytes$$

And with storing cute cat photos with approximately size of 3MB(3×10^6 bytes):

$$\frac{5.19 \times 10^{25}}{3 \times 10^6} \approx 1.73 \times 10^{19}photos$$

¹Note that the calculation on this section was done with use of ChatGPT-4o[[OpenAI\(2024\)](#)].

For 4TB storage for comparison:

$$4,000,000,000,000\text{byte}/3,000,000\text{byte} \approx 1,333,333\text{photos}$$

With quantum state preserved in repeated collision of producing blackhole, photos of cute cat can be stored at least 1.2975×10^{13} times more than 4TB storage.

3 Discussion

This short idea suggest the use of particle collider with minimum size of producing black hole can be reused as an quantum information storage that can achieve repeatable amount of data while reproduced in repeated collisions.

4 Limitation

Creating a black hole using the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and maintaining its phase stability presents significant challenges due to the extreme conditions required². The energy requirements for generating a mini black hole are beyond current technological capabilities, and the energy must be concentrated in an incredibly small space with high precision. Additionally, Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle complicates the precise control of particle position and momentum, making it difficult to maintain the exact phase of the black hole. Quantum fluctuations at high energy levels further add to the unpredictability of particle interactions.

Gravitational interactions pose another set of challenges. Microgravity variations during the black hole formation process can significantly affect its stability, and according to Stephen Hawking's theory, mini black holes can rapidly evaporate through Hawking radiation, complicating efforts to maintain phase stability. The complexity of particle collisions also adds to the difficulty, as achieving the necessary precision in collision angle, speed, and energy is a formidable task. Nonlinear interactions during these collisions can lead to unpredictable and complex phenomena.

Environmental factors and technological limitations further exacerbate these challenges. External interference from minor vibrations, temperature fluctuations, and electromagnetic noise can affect the black hole's phase stability. Maintaining the necessary high-energy state conditions, such as vacuum and extreme temperatures, in a laboratory setting is technically demanding. Additionally, the limitations of current measurement and control technologies make it difficult to precisely monitor and maintain the black hole's state, requiring significant advancements in ultra-fast, ultra-precise control systems to mitigate even small errors that could impact stability.

5 Conclusion

Creating a black hole using the LHC and maintaining its phase stability involves numerous complex conditions and variables³. Overcoming challenges related to energy requirements, quantum mechanical uncertainty, gravitational interactions, particle collision complexity, environmental factors, and technological limitations will require significant technological advancements and innovation.

References

[Hawking(1974)] Stephen W Hawking. Black hole explosions? *Nature*, 248(5443):30–31, 1974.

[Giddings and Thomas(2002)] Steven B Giddings and Scott Thomas. High energy colliders as black hole factories: The end of short distance physics. *Physical Review D*, 65(5):056010, 2002.

[OpenAI(2024)] OpenAI. Chatgpt-4, 2024. URL <https://www.openai.com/chatgpt>. Accessed: 2024-07-02.

²Note that this section was written with use of ChatGPT-4o[OpenAI(2024)].

³Note that this section was written with use of ChatGPT-4o[OpenAI(2024)].